

D7.3

Communication tools – Version I

PoDIUM

PDI connectivity and cooperation enablers building trust and sustainability for CCAM

Horizon Innovation Actions | Project No. 101069547
Call HORIZON-CL5-2021-D6-01

Co-funded by
the European Union

Dissemination level	Public (PU)
Type of deliverable	DEC – Websites, patent, filings, videos, etc.
Work package	WP7 – Dissemination, exploitation and international cooperation
Deliverable number	D7.3 Communication tools - Version I
Status - version, date	V1, 31/03/2023
Deliverable leader	ERTICO – ITS Europe
Contractual date of delivery	31/03/2023
Keywords	PoDIUM, communication, website, social media, printed material

Quality Control

	Name	Organisation	Date
Peer review 1	Daniele Brevi	LINKS	17/03/2023
Peer review 2	Markus Wimmer	NOKIA	03/03/2023

Version History

Version	Date	Author	Summary of changes
01	03/03/2023	Céline Lefort - ERTICO	First draft of document
02	20/03/2023	Céline Lefort – ERTICO, Sevi Christoforou and Nikoletta Karitsioti – ICCS	Version improved after internal review and comments from ICCS
1	31/03/2023	Céline Lefort – ERTICO	Added figures for the roll-up banner, leaflet, and poster, and finalisation of the document

Legal Disclaimer

Co-funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the granting authority, CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. The information in this document is provided “as is”, and no guarantee or warranty is given that it is fit for any specific purpose. The PoDIUM project Consortium members shall have no liability for damages of any kind including without limitation direct, special, indirect, or consequential damages that may result from the use of these materials subject to any liability which is mandatory due to applicable law.

Table of contents

- Quality Control..... 2
- Version History 2
- Legal Disclaimer 2
- List of figures..... 4
- List of abbreviations and acronyms..... 5
- 5
- Executive Summary..... 6**
- 1. Introduction..... 7**
 - 1.1. Project introduction 7
 - 1.2. Purpose of the deliverable 7
 - 1.3. Intended audience..... 7
- 2. Digital media 8**
 - 2.1. PoDIUM website..... 8
 - 2.1.1. Structure and content 8
 - 2.1.1.1. Home page..... 8
 - 2.1.1.2. About 9
 - 2.1.1.3. Living Labs..... 10
 - 2.1.1.4. News & Events..... 10
 - 2.1.1.5. Library..... 11
 - 2.1.1.6. Contact 11
 - 2.1.2. Monitoring 12
 - 2.2. Social media channels 12
 - 2.2.1. LinkedIn 12
 - 2.2.2. Twitter..... 13
 - 2.3. Newsletter..... 14
 - 2.4. Videos 14
 - 2.5. Internal communication tools 14
- 3. Printed media 15**
 - 3.1. Roll-up banner 15
 - 3.2. Flyers 15
 - 3.3. Posters..... 16
- 4. Conclusion..... 18**

List of figures

Figure 1: PoDIUM website – Home page (top part).....	8
Figure 2: PoDIUM website – Home page (bottom part)	9
Figure 3: PoDIUM website – About page (top part).....	9
Figure 4: PoDIUM website – About page (consortium section).....	10
Figure 5: PoDIUM website – Living Labs page.....	10
Figure 6: PoDIUM website – Events section.....	11
Figure 7: PoDIUM website – Library page (promotional materials section).....	11
Figure 8: PoDIUM website – Contact page.....	12
Figure 9: Screenshot of the PoDIUM LinkedIn page	13
Figure 10: Screenshot of the PoDIUM Twitter account	14
Figure 11: PoDIUM roll-up banner	15
Figure 12: PoDIUM leaflet	16
Figure 13: PoDIUM poster.....	17

Abbreviation	Meaning
CCAM	Connected, Cooperative and Automated Mobility
C-ITS	Cooperative and Intelligent Transport Systems
EU	European Union
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MEC	Multi-Access Edge Computing
PDI	Physical and Digital Infrastructure
UC	Use Case
VRU	Vulnerable Road Users
WP	Work Package

List of abbreviations and acronyms

Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the various communication tools of the PoDIUM project, their main features and how they will be used to support the PoDIUM communication strategy and plan and maximise the impact of the project's communication. The tools that will be developed cover both electronic media and printed media. This ensures that the right type of communication materials is used depending on the communication or dissemination activity that is conducted. The tools at the disposal of the consortium include a website, a Twitter and LinkedIn page, a biannual newsletter, videos, a roll-up banner, flyers, and posters. All communication materials will be in line with the project's brand identity to ensure the cohesive representation of PoDIUM.

The structure of this deliverable is as follows:

- Chapter 1 (Introduction) provides a brief description of PoDIUM, explains the purpose of this deliverable and gives information on the target audience of the document.
- Chapter 2 (Digital media) presents the digital media developed as part of the project. The digital media include the PoDIUM website, social media channels, newsletter, videos, and internal communication tools at the disposal of the consortium.
- Chapter 3 (Printed media) outlines the printed media of the project, which include the roll-up banner, flyers, and posters.
- Chapter 4 (Conclusions) provides concluding remarks.

This deliverable will be updated at M18 to assess the relevance of the communication tools of the project.

1. Introduction

1.1. Project introduction

PoDIUM aims to support advanced Use Cases (UC) of connected and cooperative automated mobility in real traffic conditions. Building urban and highway UCs on the facilities of 3 well-equipped Living Labs in Germany, Italy and Spain, PoDIUM will tackle all the different requirements for availability and performance of connectivity as well as the different cooperation enablers per UC. The proposed UCs aim to advance a set of key technologies both in the physical and digital part of the infrastructure. In particular, the following non-exhaustive list of contributions will be pursued:

- A multi-connectivity approach to ensure reliability, availability and redundancy of the Physical and Digital Infrastructure (PDI) system.
- Advance data fusion and integration of Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) to the proposed hybrid data management environment to enable enhanced environment perception models towards digital twins.
- New Cooperative and Intelligent Transport Systems (C-ITS) messages for enabling the specific advanced Connected, Cooperative and Automated Mobility (CCAM) use cases.
- Ensure software integrity, trust and truthfulness of CCAM data, their exchange and their processing.
- Demonstration of urban and highway use cases in a diverse set of configurations with integration of Vulnerable Road Users (VRU).

1.2. Purpose of the deliverable

The purpose of Deliverable D7.3 *Communication tools* is to present the different tools developed as part of the project to support its communication strategy and ensure that the materials that are produced are in line with the project's brand identity. This document describes both the digital and printed materials that will be developed to promote PoDIUM.

This document is complementary to Deliverable D7.1 *Brand identity and guidelines* and Deliverable D7.2 *Communication strategy and plan*. Deliverable D7.1 presents the brand identity and guidelines related to the PoDIUM brand to ensure its consistent representation in all communication and dissemination activities carried out by the consortium partners. It also describes the different templates that have been developed, including a Word template for deliverables and a PowerPoint template for presentations. Deliverable D7.2 sets out the communication strategy of the PoDIUM project and provides details about the target audiences, stakeholders, dissemination channels that the project will focus its efforts on.

1.3. Intended audience

This is a public document. For the consortium of PoDIUM, this document is intended to serve as a reference document explaining the structure of the website and listing the different tools supporting the communication and dissemination activities of the project. For external stakeholders and the broader public, this deliverable helps create an understanding of the different tools and promotional materials of the project and how to access them.

2. Digital media

2.1. PoDIUM website

The PoDIUM website can be accessed through the following link: www.podium-project.eu. It acts as a one stop-place containing the most important information about the project, presented in a clear and accessible way to the general public. The website has been launched at M5 (February 2023) and has been developed by ERTICO, who will keep it continuously updated to make sure the information it contains remains correct and relevant.

Some pages of the website might not be immediately published online and will only be available at a later stage and when the relevant content is available, such as some sections of the library page. All sections described below have been developed and are part of the structure of the website. They will be published as soon as content has been added.

2.1.1. Structure and content

The PoDIUM website is structured as follows below. The menu of the website listing the different pages remains visible on top of all the pages. Each page also includes a footer containing the PoDIUM logo, links to social media channels, EU funding acknowledgment, and the cookies policy and privacy policy.

2.1.1.1. Home page

- <https://podium-project.eu/>
- Short description of PoDIUM with link to About page
- Key facts and figures about the project
- Short overview of the project’s objectives
- Latest news: this section will show the last 3 news articles that were published
- Form to sign up for the PoDIUM newsletter
- Module with the latest tweets from the PoDIUM Twitter account

Figure 1: PoDIUM website – Home page (top part)

Figure 2: PoDIUM website – Home page (bottom part)

2.1.1.2. About

- <https://podium-project.eu/about/>
- Longer, more detailed description of the project
- Key facts and figures about the project
- List of the objectives of the project
- Logos of the consortium partners, with a short description and link to their websites in a pop-in window

Figure 3: PoDIUM website – About page (top part)

Figure 4: PoDIUM website – About page (consortium section)

2.1.1.3. Living Labs

- <https://podium-project.eu/living-labs/>
- Map of Europe showing the location of the Living Labs and the use cases
- Description of the use cases and of the Living Labs
- Detailed description of the use cases for each Living Lab, as well as logos of the partners involved, on separate sub-pages

Figure 5: PoDIUM website – Living Labs page

2.1.1.4. News & Events

- <https://podium-project.eu/news-events/>
- List of the last three news articles that were published, with a link to see all news articles
- List of three upcoming events, with a link to see all events, including previous events
- Form to sign up for the PoDIUM newsletter

Figure 6: PoDIUM website – Events section

2.1.1.5. Library

- <https://podium-project.eu/library/>
- List of public deliverables, publications, media (photos or videos developed as part of the project), promotional materials (such as leaflet, logo package, etc.), and articles mentioning the project

Figure 7: PoDIUM website – Library page (promotional materials section)

2.1.1.6. Contact

- <https://podium-project.eu/contact/>
- Contact form and email addresses of the Project Coordinator and the Communication Manager
- Form to sign up for the PoDIUM newsletter

Figure 8: PoDIUM website – Contact page

2.1.2. Monitoring

The website will be monitored using Google Analytics. This will provide statistics on the usage of the website, the audience accessing the website, and the pages most visited, among other metrics. This will help ensure that the website performs in line with the KPIs set in Deliverable D7.2 *Communication strategy and plan*, analyse strong points and weaknesses of the website and take appropriate measures if needed. The KPI for the number of visitors per month of the website is at least 50 visitors in Year 1, at least 100 visitors in Year 2, and at least 150 visitors in Year 3.

2.2. Social media channels

2.2.1. LinkedIn

A LinkedIn company page, [PoDIUM Project](#), has been created for the project by ICCS, who will manage the page. All major updates, announcements, developments, and any other relevant and interesting content will be shared on this page on a regular basis. All PoDIUM partners should follow the page and interact with its contents to help promote it to their own networks.

Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) have also been set for the number of followers of the LinkedIn page of the project, which is set to 75 followers in Year 1, 100 followers in Year 2, and 150 followers in Year 3. The LinkedIn page counted 72 followers on 20 March 2023.

Figure 9: Screenshot of the PoDIUM LinkedIn page

2.2.2. Twitter

A Twitter account has also been developed for the project, [@PoDIUM_EU](#). This account will be used to share news regarding the project’s activities and achievements and to interact with relevant stakeholders. Consortium partners should follow the Twitter account and use the hashtag #PoDIUM_EU when posting about the project to help monitor posts and to increase the awareness of the project. The project’s Twitter account has been created and is managed by ICCS. The number of followers of the PoDIUM Twitter account on 20 March 2023 was 26 followers.

The KPI set for the number of PoDIUM hashtags (#PoDIUM_EU) used on Twitter set in Deliverable D7.2 *Communication strategy and plan* is 60 hashtags in Year 1, 100 hashtags in Year 2, and 140 hashtags in Year 3.

Figure 10: Screenshot of the PoDIUM Twitter account

2.3. Newsletter

A newsletter will be developed and sent out twice a year to inform all interested stakeholders of the latest news and developments of the project. To comply with GDPR, the newsletter will only be sent out to a mailing list of subscribers who have actively signed up to receive it, using the subscription form available on the PoDIUM website. The subscriber database has been set up using MailChimp.

The newsletter will feature the latest project news, upcoming events, milestones and achievements. It will be promoted on the PoDIUM website and social media channels, as well as on the Zenodo Community of the project. The consortium partners will also circulate the newsletter through their own channels to increase its outreach. All partners are invited to contribute to the content of the newsletter.

2.4. Videos

At the beginning of the second year of the project, short videos will be created to promote the project and raise awareness of PoDIUM, taking into account the intended audience. In addition, one professional video will also be produced. The videos will be published on the PoDIUM website and will be shared on the project’s and the partners’ social media channels. A YouTube channel for the project may be created if needed to publish them. The PoDIUM project will create at least 1 video in Year 1, and at least 2 videos in Year 2, as set out in the KPIs in Deliverable D7.2.

2.5. Internal communication tools

Different internal communication tools are also at the disposal of the consortium. The PoDIUM brand identity and guidelines, including the different versions of the logo, and the deliverable and PowerPoint templates are described in detail in Deliverable D7.1 *Brand identity and guidelines* and will help ensure that the PoDIUM brand is used consistently by the consortium in all their communication and dissemination activities.

developed to provide more information on technical aspects of the project, such as the use cases and PDI technologies. The leaflet will be updated as necessary and needed during the lifetime of the project.

The leaflet will be distributed at various external events and conferences and at PoDIUM meetings. A digital version of the leaflet will also be publicly available to download on the project’s website.

Figure 12: PoDIUM leaflet

3.3. Posters

A poster presenting key information on PoDIUM has also been developed at M6 (March 2023). Other posters may also be produced if needed to highlight specific results and achievements or any other aspect of the project. They may be translated in different languages for participation in local events aimed at national audiences.

PoDIUM
Accelerating the implementation
of CCAM technology

PoDIUM is an Horizon Europe Project that will identify and assess the connectivity and cooperation enablers to reach higher levels of automation and advance important Physical and Digital Infrastructure (PDI) technologies, through a multi-connectivity approach and an interoperable and hybrid data management environment.

36 months

24 partners

3 Living Labs

OBJECTIVES

PoDIUM will facilitate higher levels of automation by:

- assessing connectivity and cooperation enablers and needs;
- specifying the availability and performance of connectivity and cooperation;
- defining methods to ensure the quality and trust of external data;
- advancing key innovative technologies both in the physical and digital part of the infrastructure;
- defining a flexible platform architecture following a "multi-connectivity approach";
- examining feasibility and sustainability concepts in real traffic conditions;
- creating new business models and market services;
- promoting the project developments to standardisation bodies and policymakers;
- increasing road safety mainly for Vulnerable Road Users (VRUs) and reducing automotive carbon footprint;

3 LIVING LABS, 5 USE CASES

Germany
(the ECT)

Italy
Turin (EC4) and A22 highway (EC5)

Spain
Burjassot (EC2) and border between Portugal and Figueira (EC3)

podium-project.eu

PoDIUM_EU

PoDIUM PROJECT

Co-funded by the European Union

Figure 13: PoDIUM poster

4. Conclusion

This deliverable listed and explained the main communication tools that will be developed throughout the PoDIUM project's lifetime. These tools will be key for all dissemination or outreach activities of the project.

Various types of materials will be used to promote the PoDIUM project, including a website, social media channels (Twitter and LinkedIn), a biannual newsletter, and videos. In addition to digital media, printed media will also be developed, such as a roll-up banner, flyers, and posters, to ensure maximum impact of the project's communication and dissemination activities.

All consortium partners will have access to these communication tools and will be encouraged to make use of them in all their dissemination activities. Partners will contribute to the website and social media channels of PoDIUM by regularly sharing news articles and any achievement of the project, ensuring a strong online presence for the project.